

Case Report

A case of acute myocardial infarction without coronary artery disease: what else could it be?

Plamen K. Krastev¹, Stefan N. Naydenov² and Emil I. Manov³

Abstract

Coronary embolism of non-cardiac origin is a rare cause for acute myocardial infarction. A 93-year-old female patient was admitted to our hospital for acute chest pain, persistent ST-segment elevation in the inferior electrocardiographic leads and elevated troponin T. The emergency coronary angiography showed total occlusion of the postero-lateral branch of the right coronary artery. Thrombaspersion was performed and coronary blood flow was completely restored. Surprisingly, the evacuated material was not thrombotic; the histologic analysis revealed metastatic embolus from an adenocarcinoma. The subsequent computed tomography of the chest and the additional investigations confirmed the primary source of the coronary embolism: lung adenocarcinoma. Coronary embolism due to a metastatic lung cancer is a rare, but possible cause for acute myocardial infarction. Thrombaspersion is a successful method for treatment of the acute coronary occlusion and provides material for identifying the primary source of the emboli.

Keywords: Adenocarcinoma, Coronary, Embolism, Metastasis, Thrombaspersion

¹Assistant professor at UMBAL “St. Ekaterina”, Medical University of Sofia, Bulgaria;

²Associate professor at the Department of Internal Diseases “Prof. St. Kirkovich”, Medical University of Sofia, Bulgaria

³Associate professor at the Department of Internal Diseases “Prof. St. Kirkovich”, Medical University of Sofia, Bulgaria

*Corresponding Author's E-mail:
snaydenov@gmail.com
Mobile: +359 888 52 84 17
Fax: +359 2 92 30 658

INTRODUCTION

Cardiovascular diseases (CVD) are the leading cause for morbidity and mortality worldwide, and the ischemic heart disease (IHD) is responsible for at least half of all deaths due to CVD (Piepoli et al., 2016; Thygesen et al., 2019; Ibanez et al., 2017). The role of the traditional risk factors for IHD has been well established (Panayotov et al., 2006; Runev et al., 2006; Gotcheva et al., 2013). The rapid development of interventional techniques and new therapeutic strategies in patients with IHD over the past years should also be pointed out (Jorgova et al., 1997/2003; Petrov et al., 2003; Trendafilova et al., 2008/2010). However, the mortality rate in acute myocardial infarction (AMI) with ST-segment elevation (STEMI) continues to be high with ~50% of all deaths occurring before hospital admission (Ibanez et al., 2017; Milanova et al., 2018).

The etiopathogenesis of AMI is mostly due to rupture/fissure of an atherosclerotic coronary plaque: it has been found in at least 90% of all cases (Ibanez et al., 2017). In a minor percentage acute myocardial ischemia

could occur through other mechanisms, including coronary embolism due to non-coronary/non-cardiac source of emboli (Ross et al., 1983; Rigatelli, 2005; Cheng, 2009). The relative rarity of these cases and the therapeutic dilemmas that clinical physicians may encounter gave us grounds to present this clinical case.

CASE DESCRIPTION

A 93-year-old female patient was hospitalized in our clinic for an acute, very intense retrosternal chest pain that occurred suddenly at rest about 03:00 a.m. in the morning during sleep. The patient was admitted to our hospital within 40 min. of the onset of symptoms. From the past medical history we found: 1. Long-standing arterial hypertension, treated with a single-pill combination of an inhibitor of the angiotensin-converting enzyme plus a thiazide diuretic. The usual blood pressure values measured at home were ~130/80 mmHg; 2. Non-

Figure 1. Selective coronary angiography: Pre-procedural (left) and post-procedural (right) coronary blood flow of the postero-lateral branch of the right coronary artery

complicated peptic ulcer of the stomach, treated with a proton-pump inhibitor.

The physical examinations showed moderately compromised clinical state, mild generalized skin pallor, mild jugular venous distension, vesicular breathing with single rales at the right pulmonary base, regular heart rate about 110 beats per minute, slightly muffled heart sounds with mild apical holosystolic murmur, radiating to the left axillar area. The mean value of the blood pressure, measured three times at the non-dominant hand in a sitting position after 5 min. of rest was 144/92 mm Hg. The peripheral arterial pulse was regular, well filled and equal of both hands and legs. There was mild symmetric paramaleolar edema of both legs. All other findings were normal.

The laboratory parameters were normal, except for: hemoglobin - 113 g/l (normal range for females 140 ± 20 g/l), high-sensitive troponin T - 12.92 ng/ml (normal range < 0.003 ng/ml), creatine kinase - 833.0 U/l (normal value 0-40 U/l) and the MB-fraction of creatine kinase - 93.5 U/l (normal value 0-25 U/l).

The pre-hospital electrocardiogram, recorded by the emergency team, showed acute inferior STEMI, confirmed at hospital admission by a cardiologist. For this reason our patient was referred for primary percutaneous coronary intervention (pPCI, symptom-to-needle time was about 60 min.). The pre-procedural emergency echocardiography showed postero-basal left ventricular hypokinesia with ejection fraction 58% (calculated by Simpson's rule). Additional important findings were as follows: 1) Moderate mitral regurgitation; 2. Moderate aortic regurgitation plus mild stenosis of the same valve (mean transaortic gradient 19 mm Hg); 3. Considerable amount of calcium, deposited at the aortic valve ring and on the leaflets. Neither interatrial nor interventricular septal defect was found.

The coronary procedure was performed through a right radial access after prior anticoagulation with 10 000 UI of unfractionated heparin applied as a venous bolus injection. It showed an acute occlusion of the postero-lateral branch of the right coronary artery (RCA) with coronary blood flow = 0 according to the "Thrombolysis In Myocardial Infarction" (TIMI) grading. The left coronary system was found to be intact. The RCA was selectively cannulated with AR1 modified catheter (Cordis, Bridgewater, NJ, USA), sized 6 F. Using a guide wire Asahi Sion 0.014 the periphery of the RCA was reached and the culprit segment was pre-dilated with a balloon Mini Trek 1.5/12 mm (Abbott, Vascular)". At the end thromb aspiration was performed by a catheter Thrombuster 6 F type II (Kaneka Corp, Osaka, Japan)", evacuating a white embolus, attached to the tip of the catheter. The control contrast imaging of the coronary vessels showed restored TIMI 3 flow of RCA without atherosclerotic coronary lesions at the site of the thrombus. Figure 1 shows the pre- and post-procedural coronary blood flow.

The evacuated embolic material from RCA was whitish, coral-like, soft-elastic substance, sized 10/5 mm (Figure 2) The embolic material was sent for histological analysis, which revealed: 1. Large amount of detritus; 2. Groups of cells with marked cellular and nucleus atypism, peculiar for a malignant tumor (Figures 3); 3. Discrete features of intracellular mucous production. The last finding as well as the eccentric atypical nuclei were characteristic for mucous-producing cancers (adenocarcinomas).

Other treatment applied to our patient at the time of and after the invasive procedure included: 1. Acetylsalicylic acid 300 mg oral loading dose, followed by 100 mg QD; 2. Infusion of unfractionated heparin during the pPCI; 3. Ticagrelor 180 mg oral loading dose,

Figure 2. The evacuated embolus from the right coronary artery

Figure 3. Detritus and groups of atypical cells with marked cellular and nucleus atypism. Magnification 10x10, coloration with hematoxylin eosin

followed by 90 mg B.I.D;4. Ramipril 10 mg plus hydrochlorothiazide 12.5 mg single-pill combination QD; 5. Bisoprolol 5 mg QD oral intake; 6. Torasemide 10 mg QD oral intake; 7. Pantoprazole 40 mg QD oral intake.

During the radiographic imaging of the thorax at the time of the coronary intervention, a round formation was noticed in the right lung base, sized ~2 cm. A contrast computed tomographic investigation was done and a presence of a lung tumor with metastases in the regional lymph nodes was confirmed. After hospital discharge the patient was referred to an oncology clinic for further investigations, stratification and treatment. The

oncologists confirmed that the lung tumor was an adenocarcinoma.

DISCUSSION

This article presented a rare case of non-atherosclerotic STEMI, caused by a coronary embolus from a metastatic lung cancer. Myocardial infarctions due to non-obstructive coronary atherosclerosis have been confirmed in ~6% of all AMIs (1-14% according to different studies) (Pasupathy et al., 2015; Thygesen et al., 2019). However, the acute coronary occlusions by

emboli, originating from a non-cardiac primary source, are really rare in the daily clinical practice (Ibanez et al., 2017). Coronary embolism could be classified into 3 major types: direct, paradoxical and iatrogenic (Raphael et al., 2018). In this current case it was a direct type of embolization from a neoplastic tissue embolus, confirmed by the histological analysis. The presence of severe calcification of the aortic valve required exclusion of calcium embolization of RCA that seemed very likely before we saw the results of the thrombaspiration. From the literature search we found that the main causes for coronary embolization were non-anticoagulated atrial fibrillation (~73%), cardiomyopathy with severe dilation of the cardiac chambers and thrombus formation (~25%), valvular heart disease (~15%), metastatic cancer (~10%), septic emboli from infective endocarditis (~4%) and paradoxical embolism in patent foramen ovale (1-2%) (Ackermann et al., 1987; Raphael et al., 2018). Other known risk factors with undetermined prevalence are cardiac myxomas and hereditary coagulation disorders like thrombophilias (Pasupathy et al. 2015; Raphael et al., 2018; Latifi et al., 2019).

The unusual in this current case was the embolization of RCA. Other studies showed that in the majority of patients with embolic AMI, embolization occurred mostly in the left main or left anterior descending artery (Kotkar et al., 2016; Raphael et al., 2018). It could be explained by the anatomy of the aortic valve and the normal coronary arteries as well as the physiological characteristics of the blood flow. According to published data, embolization of RCA occurred much rarer (Kotkar et al., 2016).

The acute myocardial infarction in this patient was caused by an abrupt "mechanical" cessation of the coronary blood flow with metastatic neoplastic tissue. However, other mechanisms of coronary and non-coronary embolism are also possible in patients with cancers. It has been established that neoplastic cells could produce substances like thromboplastin, activating the coagulation cascade and causing the so called "migrating phlebothrombosis", first described by A. Trousseau in 1865 and named after him (the Trousseau syndrome) (Ikushima et al., 2016). This syndrome could be associated with development of AMI due to thrombotic embolization or/and formation of a thrombus inside the coronaries due to the pro-coagulation state.

When a cancer is associated with embolic coronary occlusion, the primary tumor is situated most frequently in the left ventricle or left atrium: it is usually a myxoma or a fibroelastomas (Granger et al., 2005; Latifi et al., 2019). Non-cardiac tumors, reported to be involved into coronary embolization are choriocarcinoma, anaplastic small-cell lung cancer, malignant fibrotic histiocytoma and malignant melanoma (Culver et al., 1987; Vasiljevic et al., 1990). In our case it was pulmonary adenocarcinoma.

In a patient with STEMI due to coronary embolization, two therapeutic strategies are usually discussed if the

onset of the acute myocardial ischemia and necrosis is <12 hours: systemic fibrinolysis or/and PCI (Ibanez et al., 2017; Neumann et al., 2019). The first one is not eligible for patients with neoplastic embolization because of high risk of bleeding from the primary tumor. In this study's patient an invasive coronary treatment was chosen. The authors searched in world literature for any published results even from small studies comparing different therapeutic approaches, but none was found. Summary of series of clinical case reports were also missing. Since coronary embolization caused by metastatic neoplastic embolus occurs rarely, most of these patients have been presented in literature as single case reports (Granger et al., 2005).

The most appropriate invasive strategy in coronary embolization due to metastatic cancer is a matter of large discussions. Coronary stent implantation after balloon angioplasty has been criticized by many authors (Neumann et al., 2019). In the authors' opinion and according to other interventionalists, who had similar cases, in the absence of concomitant obstructive coronary atherosclerotic plaque, the optimal approach should be angioplasty with thrombaspiration, without coronary stenting (Ibanez et al., 2017; Neumann et al., 2019). The latter would require prolonged double antiplatelet combination, which could increase the bleeding risk in patient with malignancy. In addition, if the anti-platelets need to be stopped earlier for any reason (many patients with a cancer would need surgery) there would be a high risk of stent-thrombosis. According to the current European Guidelines for myocardial revascularization, in most of the STEMI cases routine thrombus aspiration is not indicated (class III recommendations) with the exception of those in which large thrombotic materials or coronary embolization are suspected to cause AMI as it was in our case (Neumann et al., 2019).

Primary "take-away" lessons of this case report could be:

1. Although relatively rare, coronary embolism of non-cardiac origin should be suspected in any patient without angiographic signs of significant coronary atherosclerosis. If a malignant disease is present or suspected, coronary metastatic occlusion should be discussed;
2. Thrombaspiration is an intervention that could successfully and safely restore the coronary blood flow in case of metastatic coronary embolization. In addition, it provides material for histology analysis and identification of the primary source of emboli as it was in this case;
3. Stent deployment in the culprit segment of the affected coronary vessel might not be necessary in case of metastatic coronary embolism, without significant atherosclerotic coronary plaque at the same site;
4. The standard double antiplatelet combination of acetylsalicylic acid and an antagonist of the P2Y12 receptor (in our case – ticagrelor) seems to be effective and safe enough in patients with STEMI due to metastatic coronary occlusion.

CONCLUSION

A rare case of a patient with STEMI due to a metastatic lung cancer embolus was reported. The thrombaspiration restored normal coronary blood flow in the occluded coronary artery and provided material for histological analysis which confirmed the diagnosis of the underlying disease. The procedure was well tolerated by the patient, without any complications.

REFERENCES

- Ackermann DM, Hyma BA, Edwards WD (1987). Malignant neoplastic emboli to the coronary arteries: report of two cases and review of the literature. *Hum Pathol.* 18:955–9.
- Cheng TO (2009). Coronary embolism. *Int. J. Cardiol.* 136:1-3.
- Culver RA, Bampton PA, Bignold LP (1987). Aortic and coronary embolism of anaplastic small-cell carcinoma of the lung. *MED J AUSTRALIA.* 147:455–6.
- Gotcheva N, Raev D, Trendafilova E, Postadzhian A, Runev N, Vandenhoven G, Temmerman A-M, Staneva M (2013). Assessment of lipid-lowering treatment in Bulgaria – The CEPHEUS study. *Cent Eur J Med.* 8(5):627-637
- Granger EK, Rankin J, Larbalestier RI, Hockings BE (2005). Obstruction of the right coronary artery ostium by an aortic valve papillary fibroelastoma. *Heart Lung Circ.* 14:266-8.
- Ibanez B, James S, Agewall S, Antunes M, Bucciarelli-Ducci Ch, Bueno H, et al. (2017). 2017 ESC Guidelines for the management of acute myocardial infarction in patients presenting with ST-segment elevation: The Task Force for the management of acute myocardial infarction in patients presenting with ST-segment elevation of the European Society of Cardiology (ESC). *Eur Heart J.* 39(2):119–77.
- Ikushima S, Ono R, Fukuda K, Sakayori M, Awano N, Kondo K (2016). Trousseau's syndrome: cancer-associated thrombosis. *JPN J CLIN ONCOL.* 46(3):204–8.
- Jorgova J, Petrov I, Trendafilova D, Dimitrov N, Runev N, Karamfiloff K, Konteva M, Tschirkov AI (2003). Left main coronary artery stenting. *Bulg Cardiol.* 3:8-16.
- Jorgova J, Runev N, Panayotov Ch, Nachev Ch (1997). Predictors of restenosis after successful balloon angioplasty of chronic coronary occlusions. *Atherosclerosis.* 134(1,2):268.
- Kotkar KD, Said SM, Michelena H, Wanta B, Fritock MD, Baddour LM (2016). Right Coronary Artery Septic Embolization Secondary to *Aerococcus urinae* Native Mitral Valve Endocarditis. *Ann Thorac Surg.* 102(4):E295-E297
- Latifi AN, Ibe U, Gnanaraj J (2019). A case report of atrial myxoma presenting with systemic embolization and myocardial infarction. *Eur Heart J - Case Reports.* 3:1-5
- Milanova MH, Naydenov SN, Runev NM, Manov EI, Krastev PK (2018). Analysis of prehospital care of patients with acute myocardial infarction in Bulgaria. *Hong Kong J Emerg Med.* 25(4):196–201.
- Neumann F, Sousa-Uva M, Ahlsson A, Alfonso F, Banning A, Benedetto U, et al. (2019). 2018 ESC/EACTS Guidelines on myocardial revascularization. *Eur Heart J.* 40:87–165.
- Panayotov C, Runev N, Jorgova J, Petrov I (2006). Evaluation of nonhomogenous left ventricular remodeling in arterial hypertension by regional LV wall stress. *Bulg. J. Cardiol.* 1:38-42
- Pasupathy S, Air T, Dreyer RP, Tavella R, Beltrame JF (2015). Systematic review of patients presenting with suspected myocardial infarction and nonobstructive coronary arteries. *Circulation.* 131(10):861-70.
- Petrov I, Jorgova J, Runev N, Trendafilova D, Grozdinski L, Tschirkov AI (2003). The global revascularization – a modern approach in the treatment of patients with concomitant coronary, carotid and/or peripheral vascular disease. *Bulg Cardiol.* 2:27-30.
- Piepoli M, Hoes A, Agewall S, Albus Ch, Brotons C, Catapano A, et al. (2016). 2016 European Guidelines on cardiovascular disease prevention in clinical practice: The Sixth Joint Task Force of the European Society of Cardiology and Other Societies on Cardiovascular Disease Prevention in Clinical Practice. *Eur Heart J.* 37(29):2315–81.
- Raphael CE, Heit JA, Reeder GS, Bois MC, Maleszewski JJ, Tilbury T, Holmes DR (2018). Coronary Embolus: An Underappreciated Cause of Acute Coronary Syndromes. *JACC: Cardiovascular Interventions.* 11(2):172-180
- Rigatelli G (2005). Normal angiogram in patients with acute coronary syndrome: searching for unusual substrates of myocardial ischemia. *Int J Cardiol.* 99:25-7.
- Ross R, Kay R, Ambrose J, Herman MV (1983). Coronary thrombosis in the absence of angiographically-evident obstructive coronary disease. *Chest.* 84(6):768-70.
- Runev N, Panayotov C, Jorgova J, Nachev C (2006). The influence of left ventricular hypertrophy on diastolic wall stress in hibernating myocardium. *Bulg Cardiol.* 2:130-135.
- Thygesen K., Alpert J, Jaffe A, Chaitman B, Bax J, Morrow D, et al. (2019). Fourth universal definition of myocardial infarction. *Eur Heart J.* 40(3):237-269.
- Trendafilova D, Jorgova J, Runev N (2010). Bare metal stents as an acceptable option in diabetic patients. *CR ACAD BULG SCI.* 63(11):1681-1690.
- Trendafilova D, Runev N, Zheleva I, Dzhorgova Y (2008). Late complications in ischemic heart disease and type 2 diabetes mellitus patients undergone percutaneous coronary revascularization with BMS or DES implantation. *Cardiovasc Dis.* 3:15-21.
- Vasiljevic JD, Abdulla AK (1990). Coronary embolism by metastatic choriocarcinoma of the uterus: an unusual cause of ischemic heart disease. *Gynecol Oncol.* 38:289–92.